

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

**Deliverable: D4.2 Space Research Services Report on
Requirements and Specifications**

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D4.2 Space Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

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Disclaimer

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NEANIAS is a project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

The objective of deliverable D4.2 is to report on final updates of user requirements and specifications accomplished for the software development plan of the Space Research Services latest release. This document reports on Space end-user communities, involved datasets and products and the current status of the Space Services developed according to the requirements, specifications and development plan initially set on deliverable D4.1 and significantly updated thanks to a survey that explored the current practices, needs and expectations of the space community, concerning research aspects related to open science practices, data access and management, data visualization, and data analysis. Results of the survey are detailed in this report.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The NEANIAS WP4 “Space Research Services” is focused on the co-design of three innovative services in the Space environment for user-communities for Research and Development (R&D). The foreseen services will deliver a springboard of tools to enrich the workflows of a wide range of targeted users from academic/research institutions to industrial stakeholders, e.g., aerospace engineering and related technology companies, but also national space agencies and public outreach bodies, e.g., space museums and planetariums.

The first service, S1, will provide the required missing functionalities that enable efficient and scalable visual discovery, exposed through advanced interaction paradigms also exploiting virtual/augmented reality. The second service, S2, will deliver multi-dimensional space maps through novel mosaicking techniques (i.e., stitching of multidimensional images/maps with overlapping fields of view) to a variety of prospective users/customers (e.g., mining & robotic engineers, mobile telecommunications, space scientists). Finally, the S3 service will deliver structure detection capabilities addressing the researchers needs to identify and classify, in an efficient way, specific structures of interest.

Within WP4, task T4.1, entitled “Space sector user requirements, service co-design and gap analysis”, analyses the data and computational requirements collected by the Space environment for the development of the services. It will further identify existing (and to be developed) EOSC Hub service modules to support the desired/required Space Services functionalities.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

This deliverable, D4.2, is a report containing the final end user requirements and the software specifications accomplished within the latest release of the Space Research Services.

The report describes the end-user communities approached to properly collect the user requirements initially reported in the deliverable D4.1 and then it reports their updates and refinements gathered thanks to a survey that explored the current practices, needs and expectations of the space community, concerning research aspects related to open science practices, data access and management, data visualization, and data analysis. The current status of them as well as the involved datasets and products. Finally, it presents the mapping of the requirements with the technical specifications accomplished during the implementation and release of S1, S2 and S3 services.

1.3. Changes from previous release report

The initial content and main structure of this document has been given by D4.1 [29] reporting the initial user requirements, service specifications and software development plan. A new chapter, Chapter 3, has been added to report the methodology employed to validate the initial set of requirements, evaluating to what extent NEANIAS services adapt to the evolving nature of space research by conducting a targeted survey. All chapters have been updated according to the maturity level reached by the space services and the results of the services assessment, validation and feedback given by the service users.

1.4. Structure of the document

The deliverable is structured in five sections (chapters), being the first one responsible for introducing the report, briefly mentioning its content and how it is structured. Chapter 2 describes the Space end-user communities (section 2.1), their datasets and products (section 2.2), the current state of the software and services employed (section 2.3) and the requirements (section 2.4), while Chapter 3 details the results of a targeted survey we have conducted to validate the initial set of requirements, described in Chapter 2, evaluating to what extent NEANIAS services adapt to the evolving nature of space research and to take the pulse of the community toward enhancing the space services co-design and specifications. Chapter 4 presents the current status of the services and highlight the technical software specifications to address the requirements. Finally, Chapter 5 outlines the conclusions.

2. Initial User Requirements for the Space Services

2.1. Space End-user Communities

Space end-user communities within NEANIAS WP4 (see Table 1) mainly include astrophysics and planetary scientists as well as computer scientists and software engineers interested in computer vision and machine learning. Service data and products may also have a high impact in planetary mining and robotics, space weather and mobile telecommunications, as shown in Table 1.

Space Community	Brief Description
Astrophysics scientists	Study the birth, life and death of stars, planets, galaxies, nebulae and other objects in the Universe.
Planetary scientists	Study planets (including Earth), moons, and planetary systems and the processes that form them.
Planetary mining engineers	Evaluate extra-terrestrial resources available in planets and moons of our Solar System.
Planetary robotics	Operate scientific payloads on remote environments through automation and robotics systems.
Computer vision/ machine learning software engineers	Gain a high-level understanding from digital images and to make automatic predictions through software development.
Mobile telecommunications	Analyse the impact of frequency bands used by Radio Astronomy in standard mobile telecommunications.
Space weather	Study the time-varying conditions within the Solar System, concretely the space surrounding the Earth (including its conditions in the magnetosphere, ionosphere, thermosphere, and exosphere).

Table 1 Space end-user communities

Below, the most represented groups of end-user communities within NEANIAS WP4 are analysed in detail to contextualize the deliverable main themes focused on the space research data, products and software toward the definition of the user requirements to guide the NEANIAS services developments. NEANIAS space services, taking advantage of the unique features of EOSC, will allow tackling the identified challenges, taking astronomy and planetary sciences to a new level, leading to cutting edge discoveries that will change our understanding of the cosmos, and, in short, paving the ground for the science of the future.

2.1.1. Astrophysics Scientists

Astrophysics scientists employ the principles of physics and chemistry to ascertain the nature of astronomical objects, i.e., the Sun, other stars, galaxies, extrasolar planets, the interstellar medium and the cosmic microwave background. They examine the emissions from these objects across all parts of the electromagnetic spectrum, namely their luminosity, density, temperature, and chemical composition. Because astrophysics is a very broad subject, astrophysicists apply concepts and methods from many disciplines of physics, including

classical mechanics, electromagnetism, statistical mechanics, thermodynamics, quantum mechanics, relativity, nuclear and particle physics, and atomic and molecular physics. In NEANIAS, a special focus is on Radio astronomy, that studies radiation with a wavelength greater than a few millimetres, and on Infrared astronomy, that studies radiation with a wavelength too long to be visible to the naked eye but shorter than radio waves.

2.1.1.1. Radio Astronomy

Radio astronomy studies focus on sources emitting radiation at wavelengths greater than a few millimetres. These sources could have a Galactic origin, such as clouds of atomic hydrogen (HI regions, see Fig. 1), stars with their surrounding nebulae, usually formed in their final stages (e.g., Luminous Blue Variables, Wolf-Rayet, Planetary Nebulae, Supernova Remnants, etc.), or star-forming regions. At radio wavelengths, one can also observe distant galaxies, in particular, starburst Galaxies and Active Nuclei Galaxies. The observation of such sources is a key tool for understanding the structure of the Universe up to high redshift; but also, for detecting the cosmic background radiation (i.e., the light coming directly from the Big Bang). The detection of such long waves requires telescopes with large diameters or interferometers, which can have their antennas separated by thousands of kilometres.

Very soon, the Square Kilometre Array (SKA¹), the largest radio interferometer ever built, will start its observational activity to survey the sky, expected to revolutionise our knowledge of the Universe. Indeed, SKA will map the sky with an unprecedented level of detail, reaching ~nJy sensitivity, sub-arcsec spatial resolution and full frequency coverage from 50 MHz to 15 GHz. Moreover, its fast-scanning speed will allow the complete mapping of the sky in a short time that was not achievable with previous facilities. To reach such high performances, it will combine the signals received from thousands of antennas spread over South Africa and Australia, simulating a single giant radio telescope. It will be able to survey the sky more than ten thousand times faster than before, requiring the flexibility and scalability of cloud computing resources: it is expected that, at its peak performance, SKA will produce 10 PB per hour.

2.1.1.2. Infrared Astronomy for Star Formation studies in our galaxy

Until the last century, scientists have studied our galaxy, the Milky Way, with optical telescopes in the visible-light, being affected by the presence of clouds of dust in our galaxy. Dust does not allow scientists to observe with these instruments the formation of stars, a process that takes place in the deep and obscured interior of molecular clouds. On the contrary, the infrared radiation can penetrate this screen of dust and allow the direct observation of the surroundings of the new-born stars and still-forming “protostars”. Moreover, the material actively involved in star formation emits mostly in the infrared spectrum, since it heats up to temperatures in the range of 20 to 1500 K. The infrared emission is a probe of the physical conditions of this material, thus becoming the ideal tool to study the process of star formation.

¹ <https://www.skatelescope.org/>

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In the last three decades, there were multiple space missions to observe at infrared wavelengths. From the IRAS² mission up to the more recent Spitzer³ and Herschel⁴ space telescopes, astronomers have acquired large amounts of data with progressively improving sensitivity and spatial resolution. These data are showing us in detail the star formation in our galaxy, and have an extraordinary legacy value with a strong potential of serendipitous science that is still being exploited even years after their observations. On the other hand, the infrared window will be still explored with new instruments installed or planned for major ground-based facilities, like the Very Large Telescope (VLT) and the European-Extremely Large Telescope (E-ELT), and space-born, with the forthcoming James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) telescope.

2.1.2. Planetary Scientists

Planetary science is the study of planets and planetary systems composed by moons, ring systems, and magnetospheres. Planetary scientists, then, work on understanding how such systems formed and how they have evolved. It is a cross-discipline field including aspects of astronomy, atmospheric science, chemistry, and geology, for instance.

In NEANIAS, we focus on the geology of solid Solar System bodies – planets and moons. Geologists rely largely on imaging data to recover morphological information over the surface of planetary bodies, while spectral data provide information about the composition of the planets. That information altogether, mixed with evolutionary models, may bring information about the lithology of the bodies. When direct subsurface imaging is not available, it uses non-imaging data as well, like geophysical time-series and potential field data (such as gravity), that indirectly inform on the subsurface of planets and moons (such as in the cases of sounding radar data on the Moon and on Mars).

2.2. Space Datasets and Products

2.2.1. Data and Products for Astrophysics Scientists

In Astrophysics, data are commonly described using the Flexible Image Transport System⁵ (FITS). FITS is an open standard defining a digital file format useful for storage, transmission and processing of data: formatted as multi-dimensional arrays, for example 2D images or tables. The FITS standard was designed specifically for astronomical data and includes provisions such as describing photometric and spatial calibration information, together with image origin metadata. FITS was designed with an eye towards long-term archival storage, always ensuring backward compatibility.

² <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/missions/infrared-astronomical-satellite-iras/>

³ <http://www.spitzer.caltech.edu/mission>

⁴ <https://sci.esa.int/web/herschel>

⁵ <https://fits.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

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Figure 1 Example of a FITS file structure (Left). Example of the content of a FITS Header, where keywords with info about the image are stored.

Image metadata is stored in a human-readable ASCII header. The information in this header is designed to calculate the byte offset of some information in the subsequent data unit to support direct access to the data cells. Each FITS file consists of one or more headers containing ASCII card images that carry keyword/value pairs, interleaved between data blocks. The keyword/value pairs provide information such as size, origin, coordinates, binary data format, free-form comments, history of the data, and anything else the creator desires: while many keywords are reserved for FITS use, the standard allows arbitrary use of the rest of the name-space.

FITS is also often used to store non-image data, such as spectra, photon lists, data cubes, or structured data such as multi-table databases. A FITS file may contain several extensions, and each of these may contain a data object. For example, it is possible to store x-ray and infrared exposures in the same file.

Astrophysicists mainly deal with astronomical catalogues that are lists or tabulation of astronomical objects, typically grouped together because they share a common type, morphology, origin, means of detection, or method of discovery. The oldest and largest are star catalogues. Hundreds have been published, including general ones and special ones for such items as infrared stars, variable stars, giant stars, multiple star systems, star clusters, and so forth. The most complete in terms of number of objects and reliable distance estimations is currently the one from the Gaia spacecraft (see section 2.2.3), that includes measurements for more than a billion stars.

Astronomical catalogues may be compiled from multiple sources, but most modern catalogues are the result of particular astronomical surveys of some kind. Since the late 20th century, catalogues have been increasingly often compiled by computers from an automated survey, and published as text files rather than on paper.

2.2.1.1. Radio Astronomy

Raw interferometric radio data consist of tables corresponding to specific signal correlations for each pair of antennas. The processing of radio data is a complex process that involves several steps:

1) Data flagging: First, the data is flagged to remove faulty records affected by radio frequency interferences (RFI) or instrumental issues (such as receiver failures).

2) Data calibration: Data needs calibration to correct for effects that may hinder its scientific interpretation. Such effects, sometimes frequency-dependent, may be related to instrumental issues (e.g., receiver temperatures) or environmental conditions (e.g., atmospheric fluctuations). Calibration is, therefore, crucial to compare data with other observations and model predictions reliably.

3) Image restoration: Once the data is correctly calibrated, 2D images (for continuum data) or 3D cubes (for spectroscopic data, i.e., with a frequency axis) of the observed patch of the sky are produced by means of dedicated software (e.g., MIRIAD [13], CASA [14]). The generation of these images involves the so-called "deconvolution", i.e., the application of a set of mathematical operations (tightly related to the Fourier Transform) on the data to restore the 'actual' brightness distribution.

The final products of this process are classical FITS files, ready to be analysed and exploited, and thus suitable for many scientific purposes, from the characterization of individual sources (e.g., flux measurements) to catalogue generation.

In NEANIAS, we will use data from public and proprietary surveys, e.g., SGPS [15] or CORNISH [16] and SCORPIO [17], covering different radio bands. The possibility to start working on SCORPIO data is one of the greatest advantages of this project: we will have the opportunity to work on data coming from the ASKAP⁶ telescope, the Australian pathfinder of the SKA project. SCORPIO was indeed acquired as part of the early science phase of ASKAP, observing in three bands (from 0.9 to 1.6 GHz) and using the 36 full-set of antennae, thus reaching the optimal sensitivity foreseen for this telescope. Thus, this project will present the same challenges of next generation surveys (i.e., ASKAP EMU⁷; SKA; etc.), both from the technical (data reduction in case of complex, crowded field, i.e., the Galactic Plane) and scientific (e.g., extraction, and classification of compact and extended sources) point of view, becoming the perfect testbench for our software and algorithms. Finally, SKA Science Data Challenges will be considered as well. Those are regularly issued to the community as part of the SKA science preparatory activities. The purpose of these challenges is to inform the development of the data reduction workflows, to allow the science community to get familiar with the standard products the SKA will deliver, and optimise their analysis pipelines to extract science from them. These challenges may consist of real data from currently operating radio facilities or simulated SKA data.

⁶ <https://www.atnf.csiro.au/projects/askap/index.html>

⁷ <https://www.atnf.csiro.au/people/Ray.Norris/emu/index.html>

Figure 2 Example of visualisation of a Radio extended source: the atomic hydrogen gas in the Small Magellanic Cloud is imaged with CSIRO's Australian Square Kilometre Array Pathfinder (ASKAP). Credit: ANU and CSIRO

2.2.1.2. Infrared Astronomy data for Star Formation studies in our Galaxy

The infrared datasets used for the scientific studies are mainly of two types: maps and catalogues. The original datasets acquired by the telescope are typically not available to the users and in many cases are even stored in the archive of the survey. These *lev-1* data are calibrated, flagged and projected on the footprint covering the portion of the sky observed, producing the science-ready maps that are considered by the astronomers the raw data for their analysis. Most of the infrared data are 2D maps in the FITS format described above, with the relative metadata saved in the image header, that contains basic information relative to the map, like position of the sky and wavelength, observed, flux calibration adopted, etc. The infrared maps adopted for the studies on star formation are a representation of a portion of our Galaxy as observed by a telescope. Maps of the same region of the sky can appear differently, depending on the diameter of the telescope, the capabilities of its instruments and the observed wavelength.

The catalogue of the sources are typically ASCII tables, in CSV or IPAC standard format, with each row referring to a single astrophysical object, identified and extracted on the infrared maps. The object properties, like position and fluxes at different wavelengths, are listed in the various columns of the table. Several catalogues, but not all, are delivered with a set of metadata that, for example, include practical information on how the catalogues were prepared or collected. The metadata, where available, are particularly useful to reproduce independently the values reported in the catalogues, but they also allow to better match independent catalogues. The most common catalogues list point-like sources, but some are dedicated to extended structures, such as molecular clouds, filaments or bubbles.

The data included in NEANIAS for the scientific studies and demonstration of technical tools and software belong to the main infrared surveys of the Galactic Plane, such as MIPS GAL

(covering the Galactic Plane in the longitude range $-60 \text{ deg} < l < 60 \text{ deg}$) [18], ALLWISE [19, 20] and Hi-GAL (covering the entire Galactic Plane) [21]. An example of the image dataset is given in Figure 3. They also include datasets from surveys at different wavelengths, like CORNISH [16] at radio-wavelengths, and spectroscopic surveys of molecular line tracers such as CO isotopologues, the FCRAO Galactic Ring Survey (GRS) [22] and Three-mm Ultimate MOPRA Milky Way Survey (ThrUMMS) [23], covering most of the I and IV quadrant of the Galactic Plane. The molecular line data are 3D maps in FITS format that include a further dimension to the images described above. The third axis refers to the velocity shifts with respect to the frequency at rest of the observed species and sometimes can be connected to the distance of the field through the adoption of a Galactic rotation model.

Figure 3 RGB image of a region of the Galactic plane $4 \text{ deg} \times 2 \text{ deg}$ wide observed by Herschel Space Observatory in the framework of the project Hi-GAL. The image is obtained combining the maps observed at three different wavelengths, 70 um (blue), 160 um (green) and 250 um (blue) and show two main star-forming complexes and several spots where stars are actively forming (indicated by the blue emission). Image Credit: FP7 Vialactea Project⁸. Original data from Hi-GAL survey.

2.2.2. Data and Products for Planetary Scientists

Remote-sensing experiments on robotic automated spacecraft are the preferred source of data used for most of planetary geoscience. Thus, image arrays, or more precisely, *rasters* are the predominant data format. Broadly used are GeoTIFF for the storage of multi-layered georeferenced bi-dimensional arrays (aka, *raster* data), and vector data such as ESRI Shapefiles for storing georeferenced polygonal, linear or point elements along their properties, generically called *vector* data. Fairly recently Geopackage⁹ was developed as an open standard for storing vector data (mainly) in a more concise way compared to Shapefiles or other vector formats.

When it comes to modern planetary missions the set of storage formats is incremented to support a greater complexity of data and the processing tools. Data from the CRISM

⁸ <https://vialactea.iaps.inaf.it/>

⁹ <https://www.geopackage.org/>

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instrument, onboard of the Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter [25], providing high-resolution pixel-wise spectra, are distributed in multidimensional cubes, which can use several file formats, such as ENVI .img (+hdr), FITS, or ISIS3 cube (.cube) formats, storing multi-band, multi-dimensional raster datasets.

Although NEANIAS systems must consume different data formats – according to the origin of data being processed – the output provided to our users will span a narrow set of formats so that we focus on providing a homogeneous interface to optimise data accessibility and to satisfy open standards supported by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), e.g., with GeoTIFF, or the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA), e.g., with VOTable or FITS files, towards *accessibility* and *interoperability* after the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) guidelines [27], a major guideline of the NEANIAS project.

The following protocols and data formats will interface and deliver data to users:

- GeoTIFF (OGC)
- GeoPackage (OGC)

Figure 4 Exemplary raster imagery over planetary surface, RGB color combinations extracted from hyperspectral cubes (source PlanetServer)

2.2.3. Other Data and Products

Apart from the aforementioned data, the GAIA catalogue will be employed in NEANIAS WP4 for Virtual Reality navigation to benefit the identified space user-communities. The GAIA spacecraft¹⁰ is measuring the positions, distances and motions of stars with unprecedented precision, constructing the largest and most precise 3D space catalogue ever made, including billions of astronomical objects, mainly stars, but also planets, comets, asteroids and quasars among others.

¹⁰ <https://sci.esa.int/web/gaia>

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GAIA catalogue data release 2 and 3 are the last releases of catalogue available at DPCT, in ALTEC (WP4 partner). The Data Processing Centre at Torino (DPCT) provides the infrastructure and operational support to the activities of the Astrometric Verification Unit (AVU) and the Italian participation to the Gaia data processing tasks. The AVU unit is responsible for the development and maintenance of the following software products:

AVU/AIM: the Astrometric Instrument Model data analysis software system, in charge of processing the telemetry of the astrometric data in order to monitor and analyse the astrometric-instrument response with time;

AVU/BAM: the Basic Angle Monitoring software system, in charge of processing the BAM device telemetry in order to monitor and analyse the BAM behaviour with time;

GSR: the mathematical and numerical framework of the Global Sphere Reconstruction, in charge of verifying the global astrometric results produced by AGIS. The GAIA mission was extended until December 2020, if new extension will be decided other two catalogue releases shall be stored at DPCT. The DPCT shall keep online the last two versions of the catalogue so versions 2 and 3 are available in the Relational Data Base Management System (RDBMS) and files. Older catalogue versions are available as files. The last catalogue release contains about 8 billion of sources reporting astrometric and spatial information. Having an online catalogue in an RDBMS allows to research data exploiting spatial criteria too. The spatial research is made available creating 'ad hoc' structure to maintain not altered the original data. However, enabling search on RDBMS have a cost in term of space, the GAIA catalogue size is about 24TB respect to compressed file size that is 1.5TB.

2.3. Space Software and Tools

This section reports on the state of the Space Software and Tools (in TRL7) that are being used within the Space Research community.

2.3.1. Astrophysics Software and Tools

2.3.1.1. ViaLactea

The ViaLactea Service is aimed at exploiting astrophysical surveys of the Galactic Plane to study the star formation process of the Milky Way. The ViaLactea Visual Analytic (VLVA) tool combines different types of visualization to perform the analysis exploring the correlation between different data, for example 2D intensity images with 3D molecular spectral cubes. All underlying data are managed in the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). The VLKB includes 2D and 3D (velocity cubes) surveys, numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues and allows for retrieval of all the available datasets as well as cutouts on the positional and/or velocity axis and some merging capabilities on adjacent datasets.

The scientist is equipped with a tool for discovering the link between different physical structures, from the extended filamentary-shaped structures to the most compact, dense sources precursors of new stars. The implementation philosophy behind VLVA is to provide a means to make transparent to scientists the access to all underlying information without requiring technical skills, e.g., to query the VLKB (ViaLactea Knowledge Base). Such ways of providing easy accessibility to huge amounts of data is offered from the very first user interaction with the tool that helps to identify candidate star formation sites within a panoramic view of the Milky way.

In NEANIAS the VLVA tool has been extended to exploit the new cloud opportunities given by the VLKB for FAIR data management and enlarging analysis techniques on the cloud.

Figure 5 Sample screenshot of the ViaLactea Visual Analytic tool.

2.3.1.2. ADN

Astra Data Navigator (ADN) is a tool for 3D visualisation of stellar catalogues (stars, asteroids, planets, satellites, etc ...) in a navigable environment.

The creation of the models takes place in real time based on the physical parameters read from the catalogues to try to make the representation as realistic as possible.

In addition to reading the stellar catalogues, for bodies where it is possible, the placement in the environment is carried out through the use of Spice Kernels.

ADN software has been tested on the Hipparcos datasets and will be extended to use GAIA datasets.

Currently ADN loads catalogues from files (one as main catalogue to generate the star, Hipparcos contains only stars, and other files to load planets, satellites, etc...).

This capability is provided through a specific implementation of a common interface.

Is therefore possible to create implementations of same interface for reading catalogues from other sources such as databases. This approach is required to allow for system scalability with the least possible impact on performance. Hipparcos is a catalogue with about 110K entries while GAIA has 2B of entries therefore reading from files, even with a linear complexity, may require suboptimal loading times.

2.3.1.3. CAESAR

CAESAR [4,5] extracts and parametrizes both compact and extended sources from astronomical radio interferometric maps. The processing pipeline is a series of stages that can run on multiple cores and processors. After local background and rms map computation, compact sources are extracted with flood-fill and blob finder algorithms, processed (selection + deblending), and fitted using a 2D gaussian mixture model. Extended source search is based on a pre-filtering stage, allowing image denoising, compact source removal and enhancement of diffuse emission, followed by a final segmentation. Different algorithms are available for image filtering and segmentation. The outputs delivered to the user include source fitted and shape parameters, regions and contours. Written in C++, CAESAR is designed to handle the large-scale surveys planned with the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) and its precursors.

2.3.1.4. CUTEX and ViaLactea Filament Finder

CuTex [6] is a photometric package designed to process FITS images to identify and extract compact sources embedded in complex backgrounds, like the ones present in star-forming regions or the Galactic Plane observed at infrared/sub-mm wavelengths. Physical objects in these images, such as protostars in their accreting phase, are generally not point-like, so their shape is not fitted by a PSF-profile. CuTex can detect and extract these objects even in cases of high crowding and in location where the background is highly spatially variable. The package is composed of two main algorithms, one tuned for the source detection, and the other for source extraction dedicate to the measure of fluxes and sizes. CuTex is written in IDL language and it runs on any machine with an IDL compiler.

ViaLactea Filament Finder [7] (VLFF) is a different package aiming to deliver an automatic detection tool able to identify complex filamentary structures present of infrared 2D FITS maps and to characterize their morphological and physical properties. It is tailored to identify patterns with a precise morphological definition, i.e., elongated, cylinder-like regions with a

relatively higher brightness contrast with respect to their surroundings, that describe filaments in the most general and abstracted way. The tool implements different methods to trace these features and determine the relative properties [8], like for example intensity, length, width, spine position and orientation, etc. The package is written in IDL and it is composed by multiple routines called from a main wrapper.

2.3.2. Planetary Science Software and Tools

2.3.2.1. ADAM (raster-serving, data access and query)

The Advanced geospatial Data Management platform (ADAM) is a tool to access a large variety and volume of global environmental data. ADAM allows you extracting global as well as local data, from the past, current time, as well as short term forecast and long-term projections. Most of the data are updated daily to allow users having always the most recent data to play with.

The core of ADAM is a Data Access System (DAS), a software module that manages a large variety of geospatial information that feature different data format, geographic / geometric and time resolution. It allows accessing, visualizing, sub-setting, combining, processing, downloading all data sources simultaneously. The DAS exposes OGC Open Search and Web Coverage Service (WCS 2.x) interfaces that allow discovering available collections and subset them in any dimension with a single query.

ADAM is a modular platform: various DAS are deployed on different data sources (DIAS Mundi, DIAS creodias, Amazon Web Services - AWS, MEOO Data Facility, SISTEMA Data facility), allowing accessing and sub-setting the available collections without downloading / duplicating the data. Distributed data sources are made accessible through the datacube layer, that exposes OGC-standardised interfaces.

ADAM offers three main interfaces for data access:

- the **Explorer**, a web-based graphical user interface to allow users to explore, access, process and download data
- the **ADAM API**, that provide a python-library to directly access the ADAM data access and processing capabilities directly integrated in the user's code and applications
- the **Jupyter Hub**, a web-based processing environment to allow users to import, write and execute code that runs close to the data, exploiting the power and the APIs on a remote computation environment (no user resources are used).

Figure 6 Sample screenshot of the ADAM Explorer.

Besides data exploitation and analytics user interfaces (Explorer, ADAM API, Jupyter Hub), ADAM allows at integrating data processing pipelines in the Data Processing System (DPS). Among all management functionalities, DPS aims at performing:

- Pipelines configuration: Besides the pipeline parameters configuration, the dashboard provides also the possibility to compute the expected cost of the job, based on configurable cost plans. Pipelines based on the open-source SNAP libraries are already available at the current stage.
- Jobs management: From each pipeline, many jobs can be launched changing e.g., AOI, start/end date, source data, and so on. For each job, progress status is provided (progress, processed products, instances) as well as estimated termination date/time. A deadline can be set to safeguard the system for overloading. Elastic job parallelization options are also available on cloud providers that allow this possibility via command line interface (e.g., AWS): the horizontal scalability is based on Docker¹¹ and Kubernetes¹² technologies.

2.3.2.2. USGS-ISIS & NASA-ASP (planetary data processing)

ISIS3 [9, 11] is a set of tools for planetary data analysis. It provides either command-line based tools as well as graphical viewers; some are specific to certain space missions (*e.g.*, for the MRO/CRISM mission) while other tools are meant for general data handling. All together ISIS3 is one of the cornerstones of current geo-planetary data analysis.

ISIS3 is a modular package composed by a *core* module and *mission-specific* modules. *Core* provides the base set of tools, settings and support data for general data handling. On top of that, users can attach specific tools and support data corresponding to one or more missions of interest.

ISIS3 is used internally for the mosaicking pipeline¹³. In NEANIAS we are going to expose the mosaicking functionality for the specific missions of the project. ISIS3 tools portability and

¹¹ <https://docs.docker.com>

¹² <https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kubernetes>

¹³ <https://astrocloud.wr.usgs.gov/index.php>

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scalability should improve to suite a cloud computing environment, according to our expertise, to which Docker containers will be used for encapsulating ISIS3 modules.

As a general guideline, as implemented in PlanetServer the user interface for processing and data retrieval will be composed by two levels of interaction: (i) a REST API providing low-level, though well-defined query interface, and (ii) a graphical web interface for the user willing to explore the data at disposal.

ASP [10] is a suite for producing cartographic products such a Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and 3D models from stereo imagery that goes hand-in-hand with USGS-ISIS for planetary data processing. Stereo images are images taken from coincident regions but different lines-of-sight, which, with the right tools, allow us to recover information on the third-spatial axis (*i.e.*, elevation). Effectively, with ASP tools we can reconstruct 3-dimensional maps from satellite, as well as robotic rover images from Mars, for instance.

Digital Elevation Models are particularly important for geoscience since elevation information have an impact in other terrain analysis (e.g., lithology, sub-surface structures). In NEANIAS, like ISIS3, ASP is going to be ported to the cloud environment to provide DEMs production for the selected datasets.

2.3.2.3. Map serving services (products serving)

Processed planetary datasets produced by the users must be properly allocated for open data access. Open data access and FAIR guidelines are to be accomplished by (i) following international standards, (ii) simplifying the interface with the user, and (iii) making every product a public asset, including user requested products.

The spatial data store is behind the ADAM Explore interface which interfaces the user – to provide access to the data – through ADAMAPI, which is a Python library for query and downloading datasets based on their spatial metadata.

2.4. User Requirements for Space Services

In D4.1 an initial set of user requirements has been formed by using the paradigm of ‘User Stories’ as recommended by the NEANIAS Agile software development approach in order to capture the description of software features from end-user perspectives. A User Story describes in a short way the type of user, what they need to achieve and why. A User Story is typically very high-level and helps to create a simplified description of a requirement that can be subsequently transcribed into development specifications. Usually, a User Story provides in one sentence enough information related to the described product feature, for which the development team can conduct a reasonable workload estimation. Furthermore, the User Story is used in planning meetings to enable the development team to design and implement the product features.

A User Story typically has a predefined structure like the following:

As a <user-type (stakeholder)>, I want to <user-requirement> so that <reason>

The aforementioned user stories/requirements were linked with a level of priority and value based on end-user recommendations as explained in Section 2.5. Also, following extensive discussions within the user base the final list of prioritized requirements was delivered. The list is not meant to be exhaustive, rather a sound starting point that can evolve over the project.

2.4.1. User Requirements for Astrophysics services

The following table presents the User Stories collected by the Astrophysics community, which are described and motivated in detail in the paragraphs below.

Id	End-User	User-requirement	Reason
RA-1	Astrophysicist	To analyse maps at different wavelengths	To better analyse different emitting components in the same astrophysical source from the same UI or service
RA-2	Astrophysicist	To reduce images to the same technical features	To compare images from different surveys
RA-3	Astrophysicist	To enhance current source finding algorithms and software	To identify, classify and characterize compact and extended sources with a minor impact of artefacts and spurious detection.
RA-4	Software engineer	To improve the software's portability	To easily share software and code within the community not being limited to available local computing resources
RA-5	Astrophysicist	To improve the algorithms' reproducibility	To share the acquired knowledge and allow upgraded experiments
RA-6	Astrophysicist	To access all observations and catalogues available for a certain sky region and epoch	To have a dataset to perform data analysis or train and validate analysis algorithms
RA-7	Software engineer	To integrate existing data access and processing components	To create a more complex integrated system capable of producing new scientific information

Table 2 Summary of the Astrophysics User Requirements

Considering the above User Requirements, the following Recommendations are provided.

Recommendation Astro 1: Increase multiwavelength studies.

The new approach in astrophysical studies is the analysis of the same source at different wavelengths, spanning a range from high to low frequencies as wide as possible. In this way, it is possible to better disentangle and analyse different components of the same source, possibly characterized by different physical conditions.

To do that, we need to: 1- access different public surveys and their own archives, being subjected to their specific query formats; 2- manage FITS files with different kinds of technical features (e.g., dimensions, resolution, etc.). A service that offers direct access to all of these data together with the possibility of combining/mosaicking data is absolutely necessary to speed up the research and offer the scientific community the most complete knowledge database.

Recommendation Astro 2: Reduce images to the same technical features.

As anticipated in Recommendation Astro 1, dealing with different survey images poses a major problem: how to compare images and maps with different dimensions, spatial resolution, pixel size, units for the flux info storage, etc. A tool that manipulates the images in order to make them directly comparable represents a service of key importance for the Community.

Recommendation Astro 3: Improve source identification, classification and characterization.

Many current source finding algorithms and software may detect many false positive sources when processing maps with complex background to generate a catalogue. Ideally, these artefacts and spurious sources should be removed from the final source catalogues. Residual false detections are currently manually removed by visual inspection in almost all surveys. This is error-prone, not reproducible, time-consuming and unfeasible at the scale of SKA. Moreover, existing source finders do not provide the astronomical identity of extracted sources and, finally in the low S/N regime, compact source detection performances are poor, e.g., parameter (flux density and position) estimation are biased due to inaccurate background estimation, deblending and fitting. Machine Learning may help in: i) identifying real and good sources from false/bad sources in radio catalogues automatically produced by existing source finders; ii) identifying astronomical object classes of extracted compact sources; and iii) outperforming detection and characterization capabilities of existing finders, thus improving completeness and reliability.

Recommendation Astro 4: Improve portability, distribution and performance.

Many software packages, code and scripts employed to study astrophysical phenomena are currently executed in local laptops and PCs and shared among few researchers often within the same research group. At the scale of next generation telescopes and data size, it will be impossible to process data using local resources, but computing should approach data to minimise its transfer and replication.

Recommendation Astro 5: Improve reproducibility.

In every science field, the reproducibility of the results obtained is fundamental to prove their own reliability.

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Astronomy is producing data at an unmatched rate. The installation of new telescopes, combined with marked improvements in pattern-finding algorithms, has led astronomers to turn to sophisticated software to do the data-crunching they cannot do manually. With more powerful analyses, there is less transparency as to how they have been performed.

The idea is to use open-source code libraries and other Internet resources to publish explanations of what has been done to the datasets, since the moment they were collected, and to make all of them available for peer review.

Once the scientific community can freely glean not only to the same data archive (Recommendation Astro 1), but also to all published software and algorithms, then we will reach the optimal reproducibility, giving everybody the tools to test the experiment and validate the results, in a sort of world-wide laboratory.

Recommendation Astro 6: Improve data access.

Datasets are described using different metadata, saved with different formats and stored in different locations. In this scenario datasets exploitation is complex and tedious. There is the need to facilitate the data access through a common approach based on a common dataset's description, standards for data format and efficient distributed data stores. The idea that will be carried forward in NEANIAS is to define and design a data access layer that will implement this approach and, while at the same time reusing existing applications and tools integrating them in this data access layer.

Recommendation Astro 7: Improve integrability.

The available applications and tools can be used to provide standalone space services but they could be also combined to create new services that are the result of data access and processing integration. This user story aims at allowing the end-user to compose complex scientific workflows using single space services as element of higher workflow. In order to reach the integrability goal the space service architecture should be designed and implemented to satisfy this technical requirement. REST APIs have to be considered to expose space services in a way that is easily invocable from external systems.

2.4.2. User Requirements for Planetary services

The following table presents the User Stories collected about the Planetary community.

Id	End-User	User-requirement	Reason
RP-1	Geologist	To improve image mosaicking automation	Mosaicking demands specialist knowledge about data and tools; should be optimised/fully automated to allow real-time data analysis
RP-2	Robotics engineer	To improve detection of landing sites and landscape routes	When sending robots to other planets a proper (smooth, flat) landing site and route are required
RP-3	Geologist	To improve reproducibility	Open data and open software are crucial for results reproducibility, although it must be improved with auto-generated documentation
RP-4	Software engineer	To improve the software's portability	To easily share software and settings within the community
RP-5	Geologist	To provide reduced images to the same technical features	To provide end-users with homogeneous and science-ready images
RP-6	Geologist	To simplify planetary data access exploration and access	To provide an intuitive and stateful data access interface to graphical users

Table 3 Planetary Science User Requirements

In the following paragraphs each User Story has been further described and motivated.

Recommendation Planetary 1: automate image registration and mosaicking

Combining overlapping images – or partially overlapping – serves to broaden the field of view or enhancement of the signal; or both. Typically, high-resolution images have limited coverage since they are computationally expensive (i.e., time- and storage-consuming), whereas low resolution images provide wide-field coverages. To have the best of both worlds – wide-field

coverage with high-resolution signal wherever possible – mosaicking must be applied. Figure 8 illustrates the what a mosaic data product looks like.

Although it may seem a simple process if we think about matching features in overlapping images, the actual details to be considered and merged, at pixel level, is a multi-dimensional problem to solve: images may have different luminance levels, pixel resolution, noise levels, as well as small distortions because of different lines-of-sight. Consequently, the mosaicking pipeline is a non-trivial algorithm with many parameters.

An automated process may be reached to provide science-ready mosaic images considering a control source dataset.

Figure 7 Example of mosaic: input (left) and product (right) [26].

Recommendation Planetary 2: evaluate and characterise landing sites

Planetary exploration just entered a new era, after mastering satellite missions around planets, moons and even asteroids, we are now greatly succeeding *in situ* exploration with rovers, land-stations and other robots to come. Roughly speaking, such missions are composed by two parts, where the first concerns the launching and the journey until the target planet, while the second is about landing and performing the route through the mission sites.

The landing sites are defined according to the mission's goals; a Rover robot, for instance, has to land in a place that (1) is flat, and (2) from where it can follow a route through a smooth path, considering that the meaning of "smooth" is defined according to the Rover's capabilities.

It would be valuable to a broad audience of engineers, experts in robotics but not necessarily in planetary geosciences, to have a semi-automated tool to evaluate the smoothness – or, opposite, the roughness – of an extra-terrestrial body given its satellite imagery.

Recommendation Planetary 3: improve reproducibility

The Scientific method is based on a handful of guidelines, one of them is *reproducibility*: (virtually) everybody should be able to reproduce a claimed scientific result, for its property of being reproducible it can be considered a scientific result.

Recently, thanks to the massive incorporation of software into the scientific workflow and the big volumes of data, the scientific community returned to the discussion about reproducibility of results; despite data and software privacy now being considered as a potential blocker. Open data and open software are basic aspects of the modern scientific method; they are crucial not only for science reproducibility but also for science sustainability. To reach reproducibility in a software-based laboratory it is necessary to instrument the whole processing chain, from data source and input parameters all the way down to results, where "instrumenting" means to track the data processing stages and the metadata defining the environment around.

Recommendation Planetary 4: improve portability

It is a common issue in the Sciences to complex software environment setups as a consequence of the very nature of scientists work: we *need* software, and so we *write* software to do the scientific job, but software engineer and user interface are second priority. That is the case for planetary data processing. Extending this issue to the need of scaling up (horizontal scaling) the planetary data processing, which requires setting up the necessary software in many machines, it means we should optimize the process of software deployment.

Recommendation Planetary 5: provide reduced imagery data

Datasets are in many times provided in a sub-optimal data format or state, for instance, when data is provided in a pre-reduced, final states ready for scientific use. The demand at this point is to provide users with image datasets homogeneous and ready for scientific use. For instance, images radiometrically corrected, appropriate datatype for the subsequent image processing algorithms and a commonly used data format.

Recommendation Planetary 6: simplify data access

It is an obstacle to have complex data access interface, it can difficult, for example, newcomers to just get the data to apply their technical knowledge and extract the interesting results; At least, a complex data access interface will slow down the process on the whole of data analysis workflow. Besides providing science-ready data (RP-5), provide software ready to be used (RP-4) it is well understood we can and should lower the data access step to allow for a simpler and more intense access to them.

2.5. User Requirements Level of Priority, Value and Acceptance

Finally, we present a table linking user stories and requirements with a level of priority and value based on User Board feedback¹⁴ (See Appendix for additional details) and end-user recommendations. Also, the manner to confirm their acceptance is detailed.

¹⁴ https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/WP04-Space/01_WP04%20Deliverables/01_D4.1_M6/UserBoard_FeedBack?csf=1&web=1&e=o7lgFh (access limited to NEANIAS members only)

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Id	Priority	Value	Acceptance
RA-1	High	8	Availability of different surveys
RA-2	Medium	6	The tool is available to process the multiwavelength data
RA-3	High	9	Use of automatic source finding tools
RA-4	High	10	Use of portable technologies such as VM and Containers
RA-5	Medium	8	Data, software and workflow available to reproduce results
RA-6	High	10	Homogeneous data access layer
RA-7	High	9	Available framework to integrate different services (e.g., REST-API)
RP-1	High	8	Able to produce (mosaic/field) images by selecting the source images and optional parameters (i.e., automated process).
RP-2	Medium	9	Able to filter regions in source images based on geographic and morphometric parameters: lat, long, topographic height.
RP-3	High	9	Data, software and workflow available to reproduce results
RP-4	High	10	Docker containers to deploy on different systems
RP-5	High	8	Able to access fully reduced image data products
RP-6	Medium	9	Able to graphically and interactively explore datasets and click-download images of interest as well as programmatically through APIs.

Table 4 User Requirements Level of Priority, Value and Acceptance

3. User Requirements validation

In order to validate the initial set of requirements described in Chapter 2, evaluating to what extent NEANIAS services adapt to the evolving nature of space research, we decided to take the pulse of the community by conducting a targeted survey. The survey was designed to pinpoint the current trends in astronomical research, the main challenges that exist in the sector, and the needs and perspectives for the future regarding three main areas perfectly overlapping with the NEANIAS space service offer: data access and management, data visualization, and data analysis

3.1. Methodology

We designed an online survey with Google Forms, aimed at potential end users of NEANIAS space services. The survey was completely anonymous, as we only gathered information relative to the field and expertise of the respondents -and optionally, their gender-.

The survey was divided into four sections, namely:

- open science practices;
- data access and management;
- data visualization;
- data analysis and machine learning.

And in each section, three types of questions were presented:

- questions about current practices, ranked from 1-5 depending on the frequency;
- questions to identify the most urgent and/or limiting issue, choosing from a closed list of options;
- questions about future perspectives, ranking a series of statements from 1-5 depending on the level of agreement;

We distributed the survey via e-mail to space research institutions across Europe, mainly from Spain, Italy, Portugal, Greece, France, Germany and the UK. The level of engagement was fairly positive, receiving a total of 329 responses. The gender distribution was 65% male and 31% female (4% skipped the question), and most of the participants (65%) were senior scientists with more than 10 years of expertise. The most represented fields were “*Galaxies and Cosmology*” (32%), “*Stellar physics, evolution and populations*” (28%) and “*High energies and compact objects*” (16%), with only a 9% of participants working on “*Solar System*” and “*Extrasolar Planets*”.

3.2. Results

The results regarding **Open Science practices** indicate that most of the participants make exhaustive use of public archival data, whereas only a fraction of them do share their own datasets and software. This apparent unbalance relates to a generalized concern about reproducibility and transparency in publications. These outcomes underline the need to embrace FAIR approaches, as encouraged by NEANIAS. Indeed, most of the surveyees agree

that the adoption of Open Science practices within the community will increase significantly in the coming years. Driven by projects like NEANIAS, this transition, although slow and complex, will eventually lead to the materialization of a collaborative research ecosystem, supported by EOSC.

As for **Data Access and Management**, the results were equally compelling. While the adoption of standards within the astrophysics community is still limited (e.g., following IVOA recommendations, using VO tools), findability and interoperability of datasets is perceived as a major concern by almost 60% of the surveyees. Therefore, the NEANIAS approach in this respect seems to be especially adequate. Also, the increasing size of datasets (>50% of the respondents deal with datasets >100 GB) is becoming a problem in terms of management, thus encouraging a transition towards cloud / distributed / decentralized architectures, as proposed by the NEANIAS service portfolio (e.g., in Via Lactea, providing seamless access to multiple Galactic Plane survey data stored in the cloud or ADAM-Space providing access to planetary data). This is further confirmed by the widespread agreement (>70%) about the fundamental role cloud infrastructures and collaborative approaches will play in the coming years to unlock key scientific discoveries.

Figure 8 Main research barriers in space research [28]

The responses regarding **Data Visualization** highlight some of the most urgent issues astronomers have to face in their daily work. In the first place, multidimensionality: more than a half of the respondents use complex multidimensional datasets in their research (e.g., spectral data cubes). To properly visualize and analyze these datasets, efficient visual analytics tools are required, and the availability of such tools is perceived as a great barrier at the moment by 72% of the respondents (Fig. 9). This surprising result clearly indicates **a gap that can be easily filled by some of the NEANIAS space services**, like the Via Lactea Visual Analytics (VLVA) and the ADAM-Space Explorer. However, there is still room for the development of new, innovative visualization techniques, deemed as necessary by 80% of the surveyees, in particular for a more effective dissemination of scientific results. Also, 42% of the participants believe that Virtual and Augmented Reality will have an important role in the field in the coming decade.

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Finally, the **Data Analysis and Machine Learning** section provided interesting insights about the way of working of the community. First, it pointed to a change in the research strategy: more than half of the participants usually exploits data from all-sky surveys, with a 60% interested in the study of statistical properties of families or groups of objects. While there is disagreement on whether next-generation all-sky surveys will entirely replace traditional targeted observations, these numbers highlight the **need for time-saving solutions to make the most of these new surveys**. In this context, services like CAESAR, especially tailored to extract and characterize compact sources in these large-scale maps (like the ones produced by SKA and its precursors), are likely playing a crucial role for astronomical data analysis in the near future. Perhaps, the most striking result is that only 1/5 of the researchers surveyed makes regular use of Machine Learning techniques (with almost 60% never using them). This indicates that **the degree of adoption of new analysis approaches is slow**. However, Machine Learning is regarded as an important agent in future scientific discoveries (43%), as long as thorough discussions about biases, limitations and consequences are made (80%). **NEANIAS can be the spearhead of this transformation**, leading the efforts in this direction thanks to initiatives like Astro-ML.

The results of this survey were presented at the **XXX Astronomical Data Analysis Software and System Conference (2020)**. For more details on the specific outcomes, we refer to the conference proceedings [28].

4. Co-design and Service Specifications met

4.1. Space Services

This section reports on the state of the Space Services (in TRL7) that are now being used within the Space Research community.

4.1.1. S1 - FAIR Space Data Management and Visualisation (SPACE-VIS)

4.1.1.1. S1.1 ViaLactea

The NEANIAS ViaLactea Service has been released as a distributed system including the ViaLactea Visual Analytic (VLVA) desktop application and the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB) data service. Additionally, a novel simplified ViaLactea web-based module (VLW) has been delivered to visualize velocity datacubes. VLW provides efficient CPU and GPU rendering on remote servers with multi-user support. The web application has been developed using Javascript and Node.js technologies for the client side; ParaviewWeb and WebSockets for the server side.

VLVA has been updated with latest UI and Visualization libraries and extended to work on Unix-based Operative Systems. A containerized version of VLVA which leverages Virtual Network Computing (VNC) has also been delivered. The latest novel features implemented include: query to the data service when loading local files to take advantage of VLKB data inventory related to the imported file; calculation of datacube moment maps visualized as additional layers on top of the continuum image; overlap check when loading multiple local images and datacubes; local session management to produce outputs and allow the users to save and later restore their progress. VLKB has been deployed on the GARR Cloud Platform Service and has been integrated with the NEANIAS AAI for the access to the private data and to the Accounting and Logging Services. The NEANIAS SMS is used to request access to the service and authorization to the public/private data. Finally, the service has been completely onboarded into EOSC, making it available for the astrophysics community.

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type	NEANIAS ViaLactea Service
RA1	Increase multiwave-length studies	Storage	Deployed VLKB on the GARR Cloud Platform thus increasing storage and data access capabilities toward the integration into EOSC under FAIR principles.
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	VLKB Services available on Virtual Machine for easy portability on Cloud. VLVA ported on Unix-based platforms and updated with latest UI and Visualization libraries. VLVA is now also available as a Docker container. VLW module to access some ViaLactea functionalities directly from web browsers.
RA5	Improve reproducibility	Cloud	VLVA now allows the users to save and later restore their visual analytic sessions.

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RA6	Improve Data Access	Storage/ Cloud	VLKB data access has been enhanced toward using AAI and the NEANIAS SMS service.
RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/Cloud	Improved VLKB access to be easier integrated into processing and analysis applications in complex scientific pipelines.

Table 5 User Requirements addressed by the ViaLactea service

4.1.1.2. S1.2 ADN

The NEANIAS ADN service has been released as a client application for Windows and MacOS. ADN has been updated with functionalities regarding the simulation and visualization of planetary and spacecraft motion inside the Solar System, through integration of the core NEANIAS C4-XR PMS service or, in alternative, openly available SPICE kernel data. The support for star catalogues in ADN has been extended and now allows to load and visualize larger datasets, as well as customizable data sources (including CSV files, SQL databases and the integration with the core NEANIAS C4-XR DCS service); the release package includes a binary catalogue with a selection of data from the Tycho2 catalogue (2.44M stars, cross-matched with Gaia EDR3) that superseded the Hipparcos catalogue as the default dataset loaded by ADN. The usability of the application and its UI have also been improved, and new features were added such as the possibility to export celestial object information in FITS format, save high-quality screenshots of the scene, visualisation of different spatial plane and coordinate system, in addition, new object categories such as asteroids and spacecraft have been added. Resource usage and performance of the software have been continuously improved, together with the graphical fidelity of the data visualization.

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type	NEANIAS ADN Service
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	Backend Services for ADN available (i.e. NEANIAS C4-XR PMS and DCS services) are available now as Docker containers for easy portability on Cloud. ADN client application has been ported on Windows and MacOS.
RA6	Improve Data Access	Storage/ Cloud	ADN is able to load and visualize larger datasets.
RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/Cloud	The service has been integrated with NEANIAS AAI. NEANIAS core services C4-XR PMS and DCS are available through REST-APIs running on GARR Kubernetes cluster for integration with other tools, e.g., the NEANIAS C4 Visualization Gateway.

Table 6 User Requirements addressed by the ADN service

4.1.1.3. S1.3 ADAM-Explorer Space

ADAM platform has been adapted to serve the planetary data under the ADAM-Space web application. It provides Mars data for the Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter, CTX dataset. In the backend it uses ISIS/ASP toolkit for processing original data products to reduced, ready-to-use data products. Since the first release, ADAM-Space has been

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integrated to Core services' Logging and Accounting. ADAM-API, providing accessibility to data for Explorer has been improved for better interface as well as numerous bug-fixes. The Explorer user interface has also been improved for the visualization of images by allowing the user to control colours palette. Finally, the service has been completely onboarded into EOSC, making it available for the planetary science community.

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type	NEANIAS ADAM-Explorer Service
RP-5	To provide science-ready data	Cloud/Computing	All products provided are the science-ready, reduced image data products
RP-6	To improve data access	Cloud	Provide interactive and easy access to image products through graphical user interface, and programmatically access through Adam-API

Table 7 User Requirements addressed by the ADAM-Explorer Space service

4.1.2. S2 – Map Making and Mosaicking (SPACE-MOS)

4.1.2.1. S2.1 Astro Map Merging Service

The NEANIAS Map Merging service using Montage is enabled on the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). The VLKB includes 2D and 3D (velocity cubes) surveys, numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues and allows for retrieval of all the available datasets as well as cutouts on the positional and/or velocity axis and include merging capabilities on adjacent datasets. Additionally, another tool, named SCUTOUT, has been developed on top of Montage to extract cut-outs from astronomical FITS images and, optionally, make them directly comparable for scientific purposes.

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type	NEANIAS AstroMapMerging Service
RA1	Increase multiwave-length studies	Storage	Deployed VLKB-Merge on the GARR Cloud Platform thus increasing storage and data access capabilities toward the integration into EOSC under FAIR principles
RA2	Reduce images to the same technical features	Computing	SCUTOUT developed on top of Montage to extract cutouts from astronomical FITS images and, optionally, make them directly comparable for scientific purposes.
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	VLKB-Merge Services available on Virtual Machine for easy portability on Cloud.
RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/Cloud	Improved VLKB access to be easier integrated into processing and analysis applications in complex scientific pipelines

Table 8 User Requirements addressed by the Astro Map Merge service

4.1.2.2. S2.2 ISIS & ASP Service

ISIS3 and ASP software toolkit is offered as a Docker container serving the necessary backend processor for ADAM-Explorer data ingestion processing pipelines, and also as the base Docker image for the Jupyter Notebooks – which counts with ADAM-API

as well. Since the last release, this container has been integrated with Jupyter Notebooks gateways in NEANIAS (NEANIAS Core AI and Visualization gateways) to provide the user with a fully capable interactive processing environment.

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type	NEANIAS ISIS/ASP Service
RP-1	To improve image mosaicking automation.	Cloud	Using ISIS in Docker container and the Python library NPT to automatically build the mosaicking from any number of images. It is deployed on MEEO cloud for backend processing and GARR cloud through Jupyter Notebooks.
RP-3	To improve reproducibility	Cloud	Jupyter Notebooks on C4 Vis-Gateway (DS-AdamSpace) for easier reproducibility and accessibility to the software modules.
RP-4	To improve portability	Cloud	Using Docker containers deployed on MEEO cloud and available for local use for different environments with easy deployment

Table 9 User Requirements addressed by the ISIS & ASP service

4.1.2.3. S2.3 ADAM-DPS

ADAM-DPS (Data Processing System) is the orchestrator of data extraction-transform-load (ETL) pipeline, responsible to launch the internal/backend processes for data source queries and download, launch the data reduction, image processing pipelines, and messaging processes and users about running tasks. It has been deployed in the MEEO cloud and it also provides a logging and accounting internal service. ADAM-DPS uses ISIS3/ASP containers (section 4.1.2.2) for background processing.

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type	NEANIAS ADAM-DPS Service
RP-1	To improve image mosaicking automation.	Cloud	Using ISIS in Docker container and the Python library NPT to automatically build the mosaicking from any number of images. It is deployed on MEEO cloud for backend.
RP-3	To improve reproducibility	Cloud	Jupyter Notebooks on C4 Vis-Gateway (DS-AdamSpace) for easier reproducibility and accessibility to the software modules.
RP-4	To improve portability	Cloud	Using Docker containers deployed on MEEO cloud and available for local use for different environments with easy deployment
RP-5	To provide science-ready data	Cloud/Computing	All products provided are the science-ready, reduced image data products

Table 10 User Requirements addressed by the ADAM-DPS service

4.1.3. S3 – Structure Detection with Machine Learning (SPACE-ML)

4.1.3.1. S3.1 CAESAR

The NEANIAS CAESAR Service has been released as a fully containerized application (Docker and Singularity) for automated source finding that allows to extract and parametrize both compact and extended sources from astronomical radio interferometric maps. CAESAR is accessible from a dedicated web interface and can also be used by REST-APIs.

The full CAESAR service is deployed on a dedicated Kubernetes cluster in the GARR Cloud platform, allowing for flexibility, scalability and redundancy as demanded. The service has been integrated with the logging, accounting, data sharing and service management services, being completely embedded in the current NEANIAS ecosystem.

From the user experience point of view, the web interface has been revamped, simplifying user workflows and providing new features, such as: (1) more granular customisation of user jobs (2) real time job status tracking (3) previsualization of job outputs (segmented images and source catalogues with basic information). Finally, the service has been completely onboarded into EOOSC, making it available for the astrophysics community.

4.1.3.2. S3.2 CUTEX and ViaLactea Filament Finder

CuTex (Curvature Thresholding Extractor) is a photometric code designed to detect compact sources and extract their fluxes in maps with a complex and structured background like the ones derived from the IR/Submm observations.

VLFF (ViaLactea Filament Finder) is a package designed for the automatic identification and extraction of extended filamentary features on astronomical images. VLFF is written in IDL language and its routines run on a dedicated server with IDL license.

The CuTex and VLFF IDL routines are executed through a webservice with a public accessible I/O interface to process FITS files. The I/O interface is based on a persistent and interactive connection (websockets) to IDL licensed server and are now being ported to an OpenSource language to be distributed on containers and integrated in the CAESAR Service.

4.1.3.3. S3.3 AstroML Service

The NEANIAS AstroML service has been developed to improve source identification, classification and characterization of sources in large-scale radio surveys. The latest release includes a deep convolutional neural network based on an instance segmentation framework (R-CNN) that allows both detection and classification of radio compact sources, radio galaxies with extended morphology and sidelobe imaging artefacts. It can work either as a standalone source finder, or as a classifier stage applied to source finders catalogue outputs of the CAESAR service.

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4.1.3.4. S3.4 LSE

The NEANIAS Latent Space Explorer (LSE) service helps visualizing complex data by extracting information and representing in a 2D/3D space. The service is a pipeline where data are ingested into a neural network in order to extract relevant features. Those features are then visualized in a 2D/3D space to be analysed interactively by a domain expert. In additions, clustering methods could be performed on the extracted features to add information about the latent space structure.

Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type ¹⁹	NEANIAS S3 Services
RA3	Improve source finding	Computing	CAESAR, CuTEx and VLFF outcomes improved with DL/ML algorithms provided by AstroML and LSE.
RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	Using both Singularity and Docker container technologies for the CAESAR service deployed on the GARR Container Platform.
RA5	Improve reproducibility	Cloud	Jupyter Notebooks employed from the C4 AI Gateway for easier reproducibility and accessibility to the software modules.
RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/ Cloud	S3 software exposed through REST-APIs and integrated to NEANIAS AAI adding capabilities to compose processing and analysis applications in complex scientific pipelines.

Table 11 User Requirements addressed by S3 services

4.2. NEANIAS Space Services Co-design Specifications Released

This section summarises the Space community user-requirements linking to the specifications released in the latest release cycle toward porting the NEANIAS Space services within EOSC.

Table 12 Mapping of user requirements with co-design specifications released by the Space Services

	Requirement				Specification			
	Req#	Requirement	Requirement Type ¹⁵	Rank ¹⁶	Previous solution	Gaps	NEANIAS Released features	Services
Astrophysics	RA1	Increase multiwavelength studies	Storage	Mandatory	Using VLKB and VLVA	Missing some surveys	Increased storage capabilities on the EOSC under FAIR principles	S1, S2
	RA2	Reduce images to the same technical features	Computing	Optional	Using Montage	Done on local computing resources	Increased computing capabilities in NEANIAS cloud and portable to EOSC	S2
	RA3	Improve source finding	Computing	Mandatory	Using CAESAR , CUTEX and VLFF	Missing ML/DL capabilities	Integrated AstroML and LSE services for DL/ML	S3
	RA4	Improve portability	Cloud	Mandatory	Using Singularity container for CAESAR tool	Only few software/services available on VM/containers	Increased use of virtualization and container for easy portability	S1,S2,S3
	RA5	Improve reproducibility	Cloud	Convenient	Using VLVA and CAESAR, CUTEX and VLFF	Sharing bash scripts	Increased use of standards, reproducibility and accessibility (e.g. employing Jupyter Notebooks)	S1,S3
	RA6	Improve Data Access	Storage/ Cloud	Mandatory	Using VLKB and custom data stores	Standalone applications and only partial availability of web services	Improved dataset description, standard usage, storage on cloud and data access API	S1, S2
	RA7	Improve integrability	Computing/Cloud	Convenient	Using CAESAR , CUTEX and VLFF, Montage	Standalone processing and analysis applications executed locally	Added capabilities to compose processing and analysis applications in complex scientific pipelines	S1, S2, S3
Planetary Science	RP1	Automate image mosaicking	Computing	Mandatory	Using ISIS3	Currently technical-dependent on domain experts	Use machine-learning based features definition	S2
	RP2	Evaluate landing sites	Computing	Optional	Using SAGA-GIS	Currently technical-dependent on domain experts	Pre-define set of customization parameters, build user interface	S2
	RP3	Improve reproducibility	Cloud	Convenient	Using Docker containers, Jupyter notebooks	Currently based completely on documentation and custom scripts	Standardise software deployment, and documentation.	S1, S2
	RP4	Improve portability	Cloud	Mandatory	Using Bash scripts to share setup solution	The use of Conda environments	Increased use of virtualization and container for easy portability	S1, S2
	RP5	Provide science-ready data	Computing	Convenient	Using official, scientific literature and scripts provided	Dependent on software version and computing resources	Pre-define set of parameters, software versions, standard processing workflow	S1
	RP6	Improve data access	Cloud	Convenient	Using scripts to access specific data products	Based on documentation and custom scripts	Interactive user interface, with user profile and products memory	S1

¹⁵ Available values are: **Computing / Storage/ Cloud**

¹⁶ Available values are: **Mandatory / Convenient / Optional**

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5. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the final requirements of the NEANIAS WP4 “Space Research Services” including a detailed description of the user communities, datasets and products involved as well as the procedure set up to validate those requirements involving a survey and collecting more than 300 responses. Finally, the technological specifications of the released space services toward satisfying those requirements have been summarised.

Space Services went through rounds of user validation tests (at least one for each main release cycle) to collect continuous users’ feedbacks to improve services’ user interfaces or user documentation. In the next period, for the final release, we expect all the services to reach TRL 8 and be onboarded on the EOSC ecosystem.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management platform
ADN	Astra Data Navigator
CAESAR	Compact and Extended Source Automated Recognition
CRISM	Compact Reconnaissance Imaging Spectrometer for Mars
CuTE_x	Curvature Thresholding Extractor
DL	Deep Learning
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPN-TAP	EuroPlanet - Table Access Protocol
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FITS	Flexible Image Transport System
IDL	Interactive Data Language
IVOA	International Virtual Observatory Alliance
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSE	Latent Space Explorer
ML	Machine Learning
MRO	Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SKA	Square Kilometer Array
TAP	Table Access Protocol
VLFF	ViaLactea Filament Finder
VLKB	ViaLactea Knowledge Base
VLVA	ViaLactea Visual Analytics
VLW	ViaLactea Web
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Features Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WPS	Web Processing Service

Appendix

UB Member	Contact	Brief CV
Chiara Marmo	chiara.marmo@inria.fr	Research Engineer at INRIA(National French Institute for Computer Science Research). She has a PhD in Astronomy and a 15 years' experience in data processing for Astronomy and Planetary Science. She worked in image mosaicking and visualisation, participating to the development of Open Source tools used in Astronomy (Astromatic suite) and Planetary and Geospatial research (GDAL). During her stay at GEOPS (Paris Saclay University- France) she was the coordinator of the participation of the laboratory at the Europlanet-RI 2020 project, working in particular on metadata standard definitions for improving interoperability between Astronomy and Planetary Science. She is now Community and Operation Manager at the scikit-learn INRIA Foundation, which employs central contributors to the scikit-learn project, to support its community.
Lucia Marchetti	marchetti.lu@gmail.com	Senior Lecturer in the Department of Astronomy at the University of Cape Town. She obtained her MSc in Astronomy in 2008 and her Ph.D. in Astronomy in 2012 both from the University of Padova. Between 2012 and 2020 she has worked as Postdoc at the Open University in the UK and after at the University of Western Cape and University of Cape Town. Her research focuses on galaxy evolution and strong gravitational lensing studies. She co-authored >80 refereed scientific publications with > 4300 citations in total (15 publications have more than 100 citations each) and has an h-index of 35. She is involved in a number of international scientific consortia, co-leading scientific and technical working groups. She is a member of the European Commission Research Executive Agency and South Africa's Department of Science and Technology HELP project, whose goal is to complete the exploitation of the extragalactic surveys undertaken by the Herschel Space Observatory during its mission and foster scientific collaboration both within and between Europe and South Africa. She is a member of the International Astronomical Union (IAU), a fellow of the Royal Astronomical Society, and a member of the South African Institute of Physics (SAIP). She

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		is also a member of the African Planetarium Association (APA) executive board and project manager of the IDIA visualisation Lab based at UCT.
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User Board members selected to provide feedback for the Space Services Requirements